

1 **Inside the cooling die: prediction of the flow profile of a high-moisture soy protein melt**
2 **during extrusion**

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16 ~~**Highlights:**~~

- 17 ~~• Dynamic rheology enables modelling the flow of a soy protein melt.~~
18 ~~• Accurate predictions of velocity profiles at multiple scales of the extruder.~~
19 ~~• Wall slip along the length of the cooling die is required to model the flow in the cooling die.~~

20 **Abstract**

21 In this work, we predict how a high-moisture hot protein melt flows in the cooling die of an extruder
22 under changing inlet temperature, cooling temperature, and pH. We use a dynamic yield stress and
23 novel wall slip equation, modelled based on *in situ* MRI velocimetry measurements in a circular die.
24 We also include the thermal conduction in the cooling wall itself in this model. Two different cooling
25 die geometries were modelled: a circular die and a rectangular die. The circular die was used to
26 derive the wall-slip equation, and the rectangular die was used for validation of the model. The model
27 predicts wall slip for almost the entire length of the cooling die. For both dies, we predict that the
28 inlet velocity profile quickly transforms into plug flow for neutral and acidic pH conditions. In alkaline
29 conditions in the circular die, the central core remains flowing, in line with velocimetric
30 measurements, after which it transitions to plug flow. The model was validated by pressure and
31 temperature profiles from the rectangular cooling die, measured using an array of probes along the
32 length of the cooling die. The model provides insight into the link between solidification of the hot
33 protein melt and the shear stress and the velocity profiles inside the cooling die. Thus, we have
34 created a scalable model that can be used to predict the pressure drops and temperature/velocity
35 profiles over different geometries and cooling conditions and enables future work to more accurately
36 model flow in the transition zone and cooling die.

37

38 Introduction

39 High-Moisture Extrusion (HME) is a common method to produce meat analogues, which attempts to
40 mimic the fibrous texture found in animal meat products (Akdogan, 1999; Smetana et al., 2018; Sui
41 et al., 2025; Wittek, Karbstein, et al., 2021). The texture of the extrudate depends on extruder
42 configuration, processing, and formulation conditions, such as temperature, pressure, moisture
43 content (MC), and pH (Chew et al., 2025; Garina et al., n.d.; Kuijpers et al., 2025). The fibrous
44 texture is thought to arise from the multiscale anisotropic protein structure, created by forcing the
45 melt through a cooling die under high temperature and pressure (Garina et al., 2024; Gobes et al.,
46 2025; Kuijpers et al., 2024; Kyriakopoulou et al., 2018; van der Sman, 2012; van der Sman & van
47 der Goot, 2009, 2023; van der Sman & Voudouris, 2022). Current understanding of how the HME
48 conditions link to fibre network formation is limited. The high temperatures and pressures involved,
49 as well as the metal extruder itself, limit the feasibility of *in situ* measurements (Gobes et al., 2025;
50 Kuijpers et al., 2024, 2025; Nieuwland et al., 2023; van der Sman & van der Goot, 2023).

51 Modelling using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has been performed to gain insight into fluid
52 flow and heat transfer in HME (Högg et al., 2025; Kaunisto et al., 2024, 2026; Sandoval et al., 2019;
53 Wittek, Ellwanger, et al., 2021). These models include the cooling die with a constant cooling
54 temperature and a pressure drop across the die. The models compute the velocity and shear stress
55 profiles across the cooling die. Kaunisto et al. (2024) and Sandoval et al. (2019) have modelled the
56 spinodal decomposition into protein- and water-rich regions. In their more recent work, Kaunisto et
57 al. (2026) included a wall slip model linked to local phase separation. Wittek, Ellwanger, et al. (2021)
58 added the transition zone before the cooling die, modelling the shear stresses as the material travels
59 through the contraction of the die adapter into the cooling die and its impact on the flow in the
60 cooling die. Högg et al. (2025) have investigated different height/width ratios of the cooling die while
61 implementing a temperature-dependent wall slip condition via a critical wall yield stress. Högg et al.
62 (2025) also utilised temperature- and moisture-dependent thermal parameters, but constant
63 rheological parameters. Of these works, Högg et al. (2025) is the only work that includes *in situ*
64 measurements of pressure and temperature, and the inference of velocity profiles from dye injection.
65 The different approaches to wall slip arise from the large uncertainty around the phenomenon, if it
66 is present at all, and if so, how it behaves (Cornet et al., 2022; Guyony et al., 2023; Högg et al.,
67 2025; Kaunisto et al., 2024, 2026; van der Sman & van der Goot, 2023). This has led to wall slip
68 being inferred from indirect approaches, without direct experimental validation. Recent *in situ* ¹H MRI
69 measurements (Kuijpers et al., n.d.) provided spatially resolved velocity profiles, which allowed
70 quantification of wall slip. Using these *in situ* velocity profiles, we will model a wall slip equation.
71 Thixotropic behaviour has not been accounted for in these works (Högg et al., 2025; Kaunisto et al.,
72 2024, 2026; Wittek, Ellwanger, et al., 2021). Our previous work quantified the MC, pH, and
73 temperature dependencies of rheological parameters (Gobes et al., 2026) and has shown that
74 thixotropy significantly changes the yield stress of plant-protein doughs. Thus, this dynamic yield
75 stress can be utilised for more accurate modelling of flow profiles inside CFD models.

76 In this work, we will present a CFD model that implements temperature, as well as composition-
77 dependent thermal parameters (Högg et al., 2025; Högg & Rauh, 2023; van der Sman, 2012),
78 together with pH/temperature/moisture-dependent rheological parameters (Gobes et al., 2026). The
79 wall slip equation will be constructed based on *in situ* ¹H MRI velocimetry measurements (Kuijpers
80 et al., n.d.). Model predictions will be validated by measurements of pressure and temperature
81 profiles in a rectangular die.

82

83 2. Materials & Methods

84 2.1 High-Moisture Extrusion

85 The Soy Protein Concentrate (SPC) used for all experiments was obtained from ADM Speciality
86 Ingredients (Arcon SJ, Amsterdam, the Netherlands). Compositional details can be found elsewhere
87 (Kuijpers et al., 2025).

88 SPC extrusion was performed using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder (Process 11 Hygienic, Thermo
89 Fischer Scientific Inc, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). A schematic of the extruder is shown in Figure
90 1A-C. The screws have a diameter of 11 mm and a Length/Diameter ratio of 40. The screw speed
91 was set to 400 rpm. The screw-section was segmented into 7 temperature-controlled zones, set at
92 40°C, 60°C, 80°C, 100°C, 130°C, 160°C, and 160°C, respectively (Fig. 1C). The die exit temperature
93 was set at 130°C, 140°C, or 150°C (Fig. 1D). The protein powder was fed into the extruder using a
94 volumetric feeder (Volumetric MiniTwin Process 11 / Typ 567-7660, Thermo Electron GmbH,
95 Karlsruhe, Germany) (Fig. 1A). The water was pumped into the inlet using a constant-flow pump
96 (Watson Marlow 505S, Cheltenham, England, United Kingdom) (Fig. 1B). The extrusion trials were
97 run at an MC of 65%. pH-shifting was achieved by changing the liquid feed to 0.1M HCl or 0.1M
98 NaOH (Ellwanger et al., 2024; Kuijpers et al., 2025).

99 Two different cooling die configurations were used in this work. The circular configuration for *in situ*
100 MRI velocity profile measurements utilised a transition die leading to a circular opening (Fig. 1E),
101 with a pressure/temperature sensor. To this opening, an uncooled metal adaptor piece of length 25
102 mm was mounted (Fig. 1F). To this adaptor, a temperature probe was attached (Red dot in Fig. 1F).
103 A MRI-compatible circular cooling die made of PEEK, with a length of 210 mm, was attached to the
104 adaptor piece. The total length from extruder to outlet was 235 mm, and the diameter throughout
105 was 4 mm. The PEEK cooling die was cooled with water at 30°C to induce a cross-sectional
106 temperature gradient in the protein melt and to protect the MRI permanent magnet. A final section
107 of 20 mm was not actively cooled. The velocity measurements in this configuration were performed
108 via MRI (Fig. 1G). This setup produces a circular extrudate with a diameter of 4 mm (Fig. 1H). The
109 total throughput for this setup was 1.0 kg/h. This setup is referred to as the “circular die” hereafter.

110 The rectangular cooling die setup is used for detailed pressure/temperature measurements, using a
111 transition die leading to a rectangular opening (Fig. 1I). To this transition die, a rectangular metal
112 cooling die was attached with an internal geometry of 18 x 4 x 225 mm (W x H x L). This die was
113 cooled to temperatures T_{cool} of 35, 50, or 65°C. The pressure/temperature sensors (NaK Melt
114 Pressure Transmitters, Gefran Benelux, Olen, Belgium) were placed at 4, 12, and 20 cm from the
115 start of the cooling die (Fig. 1J). The total throughput for this setup was 1.6 kg/h. This setup is
116 referred to as the “rectangular die” hereafter. Using these sensors, we obtained pressure and
117 temperature profiles from the transition die to the end of the cooling die.

118 Extrudate samples were collected at the outlet and were put in a zip-lock bag and immediately frozen
119 at -18°C. pH measurements were performed on thawed samples by cutting up 1.5 g of material and
120 mixing with 5 mL of 0.75% KCl for 1 hour and then measuring the pH of the suspension using a pH
121 meter (pH 1100L, VWR International, Pennsylvania, USA). The pH of the protein dough was only
122 determined by the molarity of the water feed; the temperature settings of the extruder barrels and
123 cooling die did not have an effect. We assume that the pH of the protein melt in the cooling die is
124 equal to the value measured for the extrudate.

Figure 1. A schematic overview of the two extruder configurations used. The top setup displays the velocimetric 'circular' setup, and the bottom setup displays the rectangular setup. A) the powder feed through which soy protein concentrate is fed. B) the water inlet through which neutral, alkalisied, or acidified water was fed. C) the heated barrel section. D) the section to which an adaptor is mounted, and which differs for each setup. E) the circular transition die, to which a pressure/temperature sensor is connected, leading to a circular outlet. F) a metal adaptor die, to which a temperature probe is connected as indicated by the red dot. G) The magnet, incl. radiofrequency and gradient coils, mounted over the PEEK cooling die. H) The outlet of the cooling die, producing a circular extrudate. I) the transition die, to which a pressure/temperature sensor is mounted, leading to a rectangular outlet. J) three pressure/temperature sensors mounted on the lower wall of the rectangular cooling die.

125

126 2.2 MRI measurements

127 Detailed implementation of the MRI system can be found in Kuijpers et al. (n.d.). Briefly, we used a
 128 0.55 T (23.4 MHz for ^1H) MagSpec benchtop MRI system (Pure Devices, Germany) with a 10 mm
 129 magnet bore size and 0.25 T/m x,y- and 0.38 T/m z-gradients. The magnetic field was generated by
 130 permanent NdFeB magnets arranged in an H-yoke with a total weight of ~ 18 kg. The radio-frequency
 131 (RF) pulses were generated using an RF-100 Amplifier system (Pure Devices, Germany). The
 132 Magspec spectrometer is operated through an open MATLAB interface designed by Pure Devices,
 133 version R1396. The one-dimensional velocity profiles were measured using an in-house developed
 134 pulse sequence (Fig. SI.6). The FOV was 10 x 1 mm² with a spatial resolution of 78 μm . A total of 8
 135 flow measurements were averaged over a duration of 76 seconds. The velocity measurements were
 136 performed with the extruder running in steady state.

137 2.3 Model description

138 2.3.1 Balance equations

139 For our model, we focus on steady-state behaviour, as it is most relevant for high-moisture extrusion.
 140 The *in situ* measurements of flow, temperature, and pressure are each averaged over a time window
 141 of one minute. We model the thermal conduction through the wall of the cooling die by applying a
 142 fixed temperature T_{cool} to the outside of the whole cooling wall. The cooling wall is assigned the
 143 appropriate thermal properties (Table 2) for either the circular (PEEK) or rectangular setup (stainless
 144 steel).

145 The laminar flow field equations are modelled by the following stationary incompressible Navier-
 146 Stokes (Eqs. 1 and 2) combined, via the viscous or shear stress tensor \mathbf{K} (Eq. 3), with a Herschel-
 147 Bulkley-Papanastasiou model into Eq. 4 (Papanastasiou, 1987). The shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$ (Eq. 5) is defined
 148 via the invariant of the strain rate tensor \mathbf{S} in Eq. 6. We refer to Table 3 for symbols.

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}] \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \mu_{app}(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T) \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_{app} = \frac{\tau_y}{\dot{\gamma}} [1 - e^{-m_p \dot{\gamma}}] + k \left(\frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}_{ref}} \right)^{n-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\gamma} = \sqrt{2\mathbf{S}:\mathbf{S}} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{2}[\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T] \quad (6)$$

149 The choice for the Herschel-Bulkley model was made based on earlier work by Gobes et al. (2026).
 150 This regularisation of the Herschel-Bulkley equation is used to avoid numerical divergence (Wang et
 151 al., 2023). Temperature, pH, and MC dependence are included via the yield stress τ_y and fluid
 152 consistency coefficient k (Table 1) (Gobes et al., 2026).

153 The temperature field is governed by the stationary equations for isotropic media (Eq. 7), where the
 154 heat flux \mathbf{q} is defined via the Fourier law for an isotropic medium (Eq. 8), with ρ the density, c_p the
 155 specific heat capacity, and κ_{iso} the thermal conductivity.

$$\rho c_p \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{q} = -\kappa_{iso} \nabla T \quad (8)$$

156 The equations for isotropic media are used, as the local alignment of protein fibrils is not modelled.
 157 Viscous dissipation can be neglected as the Brinkman number $Br \approx 0.02$, for typical conditions (Coelho
 158 & Pinho, 2009). Details are shown in Section SI.1. The symmetry boundary condition on the mirror
 159 planes utilises Eqs. 9 and 10 for flow and temperature, respectively. These are only utilised for the
 160 rectangular setup.

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\nabla T \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (10)$$

161

162 2.3.2 Initial and boundary conditions

163 The wall slip is governed by Navier Slip (Eq. 11) via the non-tangential stress tensor \mathbf{K}_{nt} , with β
 164 including a temperature- and pH-dependence (Table 1). At the inlet of the die, we utilise a no-slip
 165 condition for numerical reasons, and we transition between the initial no-slip to the slip condition
 166 using a sigmoidal ramp function (Fig. SI.5). The inflow of material is governed by a constant
 167 throughput boundary condition (Eq. 12), where the total integral over the inlet surface $\partial\Omega$ yields the
 168 throughput \dot{m} . The outflow of material is governed by a static boundary pressure p_0 of 1 bar (Eq. 13).

$$\mathbf{K}_{nt} = -\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\beta} \mathbf{u}_{slip} \quad (11)$$

$$-\int_{\partial\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) d_{bc} dS = \dot{m} \quad (12)$$

$$[-\rho\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{K}]\mathbf{n} = -p_0\mathbf{I} \quad (13)$$

169 The thermal boundary condition of the inlet is governed by Eqs. 14 and 15, with T_{inlet} being the
 170 temperature at the inlet. The temperature of the cooling die wall is governed by a Dirichlet condition
 171 using a constant temperature T_{cool} (Eq. 16). The outflow boundary is governed by Eq. 17. We note
 172 that the heat capacity C_p is dependent on moisture and temperature (Eq. 18). We vary either the
 173 inlet temperature T_{inlet} and the pH, or only the cooling temperature T_{cool} , according to the measured
 174 values. The temperature T_{cool} for the circular die are taken from the adaptor die (Fig. 1F, Table SI.2)
 175 and for the rectangular die from the transition die (Fig. 1I). The pH is set at the measured values of
 176 5.9, 7.1, or 8.6 for the circular die, or 4.8, 7.4, and 8.9 for the rectangular die.

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q} = \rho\Delta H \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta H = C_p T_{inlet} \quad (15)$$

$$T = T_{cool} \quad (16)$$

$$-\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad (17)$$

177 2.3.3 Material parameters

178 The parameters used in the equations above are defined in Table 1, either as constants or variables
 179 with a dependency on the glass transition temperature T_g , MC, temperature T , and/or pH. The
 180 moisture M and pH are set as constants, and the temperature T is the local temperature of the model.
 181 All variables are calculated locally per element. To smoothly transition from a no-slip condition to the
 182 slip condition, a sigmoidal normalisation function $r(x)$ is used, where x is the position along the length
 183 of the cooling die (Eq. 26, Fig. SI.5). The glass transition temperature is dependent on MC (Eq. 28).
 184 The constants in equation 28 can be found in section SI.3.

Table 1: Material parameters and their equation or constant value.

Parameter	Value	Source	Eq.
Heat capacity C_p	$2341.64 + 12.01MC + 3.90T$ [J/K]	(Högg & Rauh, 2023)	(18)
Dynamic yield stress τ_y	$10^{(27.2 \cdot T_g/T - 0.038pH - 10.2)}$ [Pa]	(Gobes et al., 2026)	(19)
Density ρ	$-1113M + 1843$ [kg/m ³]	(Högg & Rauh, 2023)	(20)
Thermal conductivity κ_{iso}	$\alpha\rho C_p$ [W/(m·K)]	(Högg & Rauh, 2023)	(21)
Consistency index k	$\tau_y \dot{\gamma}_{cr}^n$ [Pa·s]	(Gobes et al., 2026)	(22)
Flow index n	0.15 [-]	(Gobes et al., 2026)	(23)
Regulisation parameter m_p	100 [s]	This work	(24)
Critical shear rate $\dot{\gamma}_{cr}$	1.5 [s ⁻¹]	(Gobes et al., 2026)	(25)
Slip length β	$(275.16 - 28.2 \cdot pH - 0.084 \cdot T) * r(x)$	This Work	(26)
Thermal diffusivity α	$(0.0816 - 0.05682MC + 0.1164MC^2 + 6.866 \cdot 10^{-4}MC^2T - 5.17 \cdot 10^{-6}MC^2T^2) \cdot 10^{-6}$ [m ² s ⁻¹]	(Baik & Mittal, 2003; Högg et al., 2025)	(27)
Glass transition temperature T_g	$T_g = \frac{y_w \Delta C_{p,w} T_{g,w} + y_s \Delta C_{p,s} T_{g,s}}{y_w \Delta C_{p,w} + y_s \Delta C_{p,s}}$	(Gobes et al., 2026)	(28)

185 In Table 2, the thermal properties for either the PEEK or stainless-steel dies can be found.

Table 2: Thermal properties and densities for PEEK and stainless steel materials used for the construction of the cooling dies.

Property	Stainless steel	Source	PEEK	Source
Density ρ [kg m^{-3}]	7850	(Bogaard, 1985)	1320	(Rivière et al., 2016)
Thermal conductivity κ_{iso} [$\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$]	44.5		0.25	(Cheng et al., 1987)
Heat capacity C_p [$\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$]	475		1090	

186

187 2.3.4 Geometry & meshing

188 The geometries of the circular and rectangular dies are based on the configurations shown in Figure
 189 1. The circular mesh starts at Figure 1F, after the metal adaptor, where the cooling wall is entirely
 190 made of PEEK. The rectangular mesh starts after the transition die (Fig. 1J). The cooling wall is made
 191 entirely of stainless steel.

192 The geometry of the circular flow mesh is defined via a 2D axis-symmetric geometry using an inner
 193 radius of the cooling die of 2 mm, a thickness of the PEEK cooling wall of 1 mm, and a length of 22.5
 194 cm, of which the first 2.5 cm are uncooled.

195 The three-dimensional (3D) geometry of the rectangular pressure/temperature mesh is defined via
 196 extension of a 2D filleted rectangle representing a quarter of the die, using a width of 9 mm, a height
 197 of 2 mm (cooling die) and 4 mm of cooling wall, with a fillet radius of 1 mm. This rectangle was then
 198 extended to a length of 225 mm. Mirror planes are placed at the inner faces, effectively simulating
 199 the entire die.

200 The geometry and mesh are shown in Figure 2 for both the circular die (Fig. 2A) and the rectangular
 201 die (Fig. 2B).

Figure 2: The geometry (top) and mesh (bottom) of the cooling dies. For both meshes, note the denser meshing near the boundary between the melt and the cooling wall. A) The circular geometry, with the initial 2 cm uncooled. The starting section of the mesh is shown. B) the rectangular geometry with the front-facing mesh shown.

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203

204

205 2.4 Numerical implementation via finite element modelling

206 The model is implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics 6.4 (COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden). We use
 207 a fully coupled model, combining flow and temperature, via a Laminar Flow interface, a Heat Transfer
 208 in Solids and Fluids interface, and a multiphysics non-isothermal flow interface. We use a mesh
 209 density of approximately 9000 and 15000 quadrilateral mesh elements over the circular and
 210 rectangular meshes described above. 2nd order Lagrangian Elements are used for the velocity field,
 211 and 1st order for the pressure field (i.e., P2+P1 discretisation). The PARADISO solver is used until an
 212 error of 0.001 is reached. For optimisation of the wall slip equation, the internal optimisation
 213 procedure was used, targeting a single constant in Eq. 26 at a time. The optimisation targets were
 214 based on the measured velocity profiles.

Table 3: An overview of the symbols used in this work

Symbol [unit]	Description
C_p [J/K]	Heat capacity
ΔH [J/g]	Heat enthalpy change
k [Pa·s]	Consistency index
\mathbf{K} [Pa]	Stress tensor
m_p [s]	Regularisation parameter
\dot{m} [kg/s]	Throughput
n [-]	Flow index
p [Pa]	Fluid pressure
\mathbf{q} [W/m ²]	Heat flux tensor
Q_p [J]	Heat changes via pressure
Q_{ke} [J]	Heat changes via fluid flux
r [-]	Ramped normalisation factor
\mathbf{S} [s ⁻¹]	Strain rate tensor
T_g [K]	Glass transition temperature
\mathbf{u} [m/s]	Fluid velocity tensor
α [m ² /s]	Thermal diffusivity
β [-]	Navier slip length
$\dot{\gamma}$ [s ⁻¹]	Shear rate
$\dot{\gamma}_{ref}$ [s ⁻¹]	Critical shear rate
κ_{iso} [W/(m·K)]	Thermal conductivity
μ_{app} [Pa·s]	Apparent viscosity

215

216 3. Results

217 3.1 Modelling of the wall slip.

218 For the case of a Herschel-Bulkley fluid in a circular die for a no-slip condition, we can estimate the
 219 pressure drop required to achieve the average velocities using an analytical equation (Eq. SI.2)
 220 (Goyon et al., 2010), which includes parameters such as the yield stress τ_y , flow index n , consistency
 221 index k , and a pressure drop, as well as physical parameters such as the length and width of the
 222 pipe. Note that this equation utilises a no-slip assumption. Average velocities of around 21 mm/s
 223 have been measured with a pressure drop of 4-10 bar in a circular die (Kuijpers et al., n.d.). To
 224 achieve these velocities with the following parameters, a static yield stress τ_y of 10⁶ Pa, and a flow
 225 index n of 0.15 for an MC of 65%, pH 7.1, temperature (T) of 115°C (Gobes et al., 2026), a pressure
 226 of 7500 bar is required. We attributed this unrealistic pressure drop to the presence of a dynamic
 227 yield stress (Gobes et al., 2026), instead of a static one that does not account for thixotropy. To lower
 228 the pressure drop, we thus implement a dynamic yield stress (Eq. 19), dependent on T_g/T and pH.
 229 We use a dynamic yield stress of 10⁴ Pa, which still leads to a pressure drop of around 350 bar, which
 230 is still far higher than the measured 4-10 bar and indicates that Herschel-Bulkley with a no-slip
 231 condition, even using dynamic yield stress, is not sufficient to model the flow in the circular cooling
 232 die. From MRI measurements (Kuijpers et al., n.d.), we observe the presence of wall slip at the

233 middle of the cooling die. The observed pressure drops (4-10 bar) indicate that there must be wall
234 slip along the majority of the cooling die.

235 Thus, in this work, we utilise the dynamic yield stress equation (Eq. 19) (Gobes et al., 2026), as well
236 as a pH and temperature-dependent slip length equation (Eq. 26). For the wall slip, a bilinear
237 equation was chosen ($\beta = a \cdot T + b \cdot pH + c$). Fitting of the equation was performed by calculating the
238 ratio of the peak velocity to the minimum velocity along the width of the die for both the predicted
239 and the measured velocity profiles. The ratio is used instead of the complete velocity profile, as
240 interpolation would be required, making it difficult to directly compare the MRI profile to the predicted
241 profile. Additionally, the minimum and maximum values of the profile are obtainable from COMSOL
242 during calculations and can be used to accelerate fitting procedures. Via the difference between the
243 measured and predicted ratio, a least-squares minimisation fit is performed. The constants of the
244 bilinear equation were fitted by iteratively changing one parameter and choosing the optimal value
245 via least squares minimisation. For the *in situ* value, the ratio of the minimum and maximum
246 velocities between the centre and 0.25 mm near the wall was used to account for inaccuracies within
247 the MRI measurements of the velocity at the wall.

248 By means of ¹H MRI (Kuijpers et al., n.d.), velocity profiles were measured at a single location along
249 the circular cooling die at pH values of 5.9, 7.1 and 8.6. The measured velocity profiles, along with
250 the predicted profiles at the same location along the cooling die, are shown in Fig. 3. All profiles
251 display similar values for the averaged velocity, namely 20.7 ± 0.3 mm/s. The flow measurement at
252 pH 7.1 produced velocity profiles akin to a standard Herschel-Bulkley profile: a flat centre and lower
253 velocities near the wall (Fig. 3). Notably, the velocity is non-zero at the wall due to wall slip. At pH
254 8.6, the flow profile has a bell-shape in the centre of the cooling die (Fig. 3). The amplitude of this
255 bell-shape increases with temperature. For this alkaline condition, the velocity in the centre increases
256 by 10, 13 and 22% for a T_{inlet} of 110, 115, and 124 C° respectively, when compared to the velocity
257 near the wall. Thus, in between the conditions of pH 7.1 and 8.6 lies a transition from the Herschel-
258 Bulkley profiles to a superposition of plug and bell-shaped profiles. The wall velocity appears much
259 higher for extrusion at pH 5.9 and 8.6, with no velocity gradient measured next to the wall. Overall,
260 at pH 5.9, a plug flow profile is observed, while at pH 8.6, one observes the superposition of a plug
261 and bell-shaped velocity profile. The simulated data always produce a profile with a velocity gradient
262 of around zero, which is observed via MRI for extrusion at alkaline and acidic conditions. The bell
263 shape in the centre of the velocity profiles at alkaline conditions increases with temperature. For the
264 other pH conditions, outside of the wall region, a flat profile is observed, with no variation based on
265 temperature. In section SI.6, we show how the temperature and velocity evolve in the cooling die in
266 detail for a single experimental condition (Fig. SI.2), as well as temperature and pressure profiles for
267 all conditions (Fig. SI.3). The pressure drops predicted (Fig. SI.3) are within 1 bar of those measured
268 (Table SI.1).

Figure 3: The measured ^1H MRI velocity profiles (blue filled circles, with standard error) as well as the predicted profiles for each condition (dashed line). The columns indicate the T_{inlet} temperature, and the rows indicate the pH of the protein melt. Other experimental and modelling conditions are equivalent for each condition. The temperatures used for T_{inlet} in the models are 110, 115, and 124 °C, as measured via the temperature sensor on the adaptor (Table SI.1).

270 3.2 Model validation on the rectangular die

271 From the sensors placed in the transition die (Fig. 1I) and along the cooling die (Fig. 1J), we obtained
 272 wall temperatures and pressures (Table SI.3). We investigated whether the model can accurately
 273 predict the wall pressures and temperatures along the rectangular die using parameters fitted in the
 274 previous section for a circular die. The predictions for the pH and T_{inlet} variations, as well as cooling
 275 temperature T_{cool} variation, can be seen in Figure 4A and B, respectively. Note that both T_{inlet} and
 276 the pH are different compared to the circular die, and thus the slip length β is inter/extrapolated via
 277 Eq. 26.

Figure 4: The dashed lines indicate the predicted pressure and temperature profiles along the cooling die. The circle markers indicate experimentally measured values. A) For experiments at pH 4.8, 7.4 and 8.9, we varied the T_{inlet} temperature (127, 134, or 140°C) while keeping the cooling water temperature at 65 °C. B) For the cooling series, the cooling water temperature T_{cool} was set at 65, 50, or 35°C, while other conditions were identical to the pH 7.4, T_{inlet} 140°C condition. The zero position refers to the temperature/pressure sensor placed in the transition die (Fig. 1I); for the other positions, sensors were placed at the wall of the cooling die (Fig. 1J).

278

279 The predicted temperature profiles lie within 10°C for the first point after the transition die (5 cm)
 280 (Fig. 4A) and are within 2°C afterwards. For the cooling wall T_{cool} variations, we see larger differences
 281 further along the cooling die (Fig. 4B). Between the predictions at pH 4.8, 7.4, and 8.9, no significant
 282 differences in experimental temperature profile were observed, with all differences <1°C (Fig. 4A).
 283 All final temperatures, including those of the cooling series and regardless of pH, lie at 10 ± 1 °C above
 284 the cooling water temperature, with initial temperature having no impact on the final temperature.

285 For the experiments at pH 4.8 and 8.9, the predicted pressures lie around the same levels as the
 286 measured pressures and follow the expected temperature trend, where lower (cooling) temperatures
 287 lead to higher pressures. The pressure predictions for the neutral conditions lie lower than those
 288 measured. This lower pressure indicates that the predictions are based on an overestimated slip or
 289 an underestimated viscosity. This is in line with the predictions seen in Figure 3, where the neutral
 290 conditions exhibit less slip than predicted. The measured cooling die wall temperatures and pressures
 291 for the velocity measurements are included in Table SI.2. At pH 4.8, we do not see clear structural
 292 anisotropy in the ^1H MRI images (Kuijpers et al. n.d.), while at pH 7.4 and 8.9, the structural
 293 anisotropy is visible near the edges of the samples, with lamellae aligned with the flow direction
 294 visible (Fig. SI.1).

295 4. Discussion

296 4.1 Wall slip

297 Only when considering wall slip along the entire length of the die, we obtain pressures in a realistic
 298 range and can model the temperature and pH-dependent behaviour (Fig. 4). The predicted velocity
 299 profile starts as a Herschel-Bulkley profile, with a non-zero wall velocity, before transitioning to plug
 300 flow. For alkaline conditions, this Herschel-Bulkley profile then turns into a superposition of a plug
 301 and bell-shaped profile, while for acidic and neutral conditions, the model predicts plug flow along
 302 the remaining length of the cooling die. The initial Herschel-Bulkley profile arises from the no-slip
 303 condition that is imposed near the entrance of the die via the sigmoidal ramp function $r(x)$ (Eq. 26).
 304 This was done to improve numerical accuracy near the start, and is based on previous work by
 305 Wittek, Ellwanger et al. (2021), who show large shear forces near the entrance of the cooling die

306 when a transition die is included. Combined with assumptions on extensional flow (Cornet et al.,
307 2022), we chose to impose this no-slip condition. There is a large amount of uncertainty in the
308 velocity profile at the start of the cooling die, as we cannot measure the velocity profile at that
309 location, and thus the profile is based on our assumption of a no-slip condition at the start of the
310 cooling die.

311 The wall slip in this work has been based on quantitative MRI velocity over the width of the cooling
312 die. This enabled a direct *in situ* comparison, which is a significant advantage over the use of
313 qualitative tracer dyes (Högg et al., 2025), ultrasound measurements, which only measure a segment
314 of the cooling die (Kaunisto et al., 2025), or measurements performed in capillary rheometers
315 (Barnes et al., 2006). By using multiple pH conditions when constructing the wall slip equation, we
316 can predict behaviour outside of these exact pH conditions via interpolation and extrapolation. Thus,
317 quantitative measurements allowed us to construct a wall slip equation that is applicable over a range
318 of temperature and pH conditions, unlike previous works, which only focused on a single condition.

319 The current dependence of β on pH is only based on flow-MRI measurements at three different pH
320 values (Fig. 3). Both for velocity at the die wall and for protein melt solidification, we observe different
321 behaviour. Additional flow-MRI measurements should be performed with a pH between the values
322 shown in this work, ideally at additional locations along the cooling die as well. The current benchtop
323 flow-MRI setup is limited to a small region halfway along the length of the cooling die, while flow
324 characterisation at the transition zone and at the start of the cooling die would be of high interest.
325 Larger magnet-bore sizes would enable these measurements (O'Reilly et al., 2021) and allow wider
326 cooling dies to be measured. With flow-MRI measurements at additional pH values, the transition of
327 wall slip and protein melt solidification from alkaline to neutral and acidic conditions could be
328 described in further detail. An improved dependence of slip length β on pH could be achieved by
329 implementing a quadratic pH dependence, as this would enable modelling more complex pH-
330 dependencies. This higher-order dependence could in turn be coupled to, e.g., alignment parameters
331 or moisture concentrations, as suggested by Kaunisto et al. (2026). Further research into wall slip
332 using capillary rheometry could also provide insights into the pH dependence of β without requiring
333 additional MRI trials (Chien et al., 2005; Corfield et al., 1999; Patel et al., 2017a). These methods
334 are, however, very labour-intensive and remove the benefits of directly using an extruder, such as
335 including the thixotropic history caused by the HME process itself. The closed cavity rheometer is
336 similarly unsuitable, since the method relies on the prevention of slip to perform measurements, and
337 thus cannot accurately quantify slip. It is expected that a refined equation could reveal that at both
338 acidic and alkaline conditions, significant wall slip occurs, with the neutral condition having a more
339 Herschel-Bulkley profile, with a non-zero gradient near the wall, as seen in Figure 3.

340 Previously, it was shown that T_g/T can be used to explain the variance in specific rheological
341 properties (e.g., yield stress, plateau modulus, flow index) (Gobes et al., 2026), and with T_2 NMR
342 measurements (van der Sman et al., 2026), the T_g could be more accurately measured in the melts,
343 allowing the T_g of the dough to be estimated more accurately. Currently used equations only include
344 moisture and temperature (Gobes et al., 2026), while the T_g is also known to be dependent on pH
345 (Anker et al., 1999; Liu & Chin, 2023). It would be of interest to investigate if this expanded
346 T_g/T equation could replace the use of temperature, moisture, and pH dependence of β .

347 Construction of the wall slip equation (Eq. 26) also poses the question of what physical phenomenon
348 causes wall slip, and thus which terms to include. With lower temperatures, the water holding
349 capacity of the melt lowers (Cornet et al., 2021), therefore excluding more water from the protein
350 matrix. This water can form a lubrication layer, which significantly lowers the friction and therefore
351 increases slip (Lawal et al., 1993). Liquid phase migration from the matrix leads to a water- and
352 protein-rich region, and has been observed during ram extrusion (Mascia et al., 2006; Patel et al.,
353 2017a, 2017b), and could be used to model the wall slip, using Flory-Rehner theory, which includes
354 dependence on temperature, pH, and moisture (Cornet et al., 2020, 2021).

355 4.2 Solidification of the protein melt

356 As seen in Fig. 3, the velocity at the cooling die wall is highest for the acidic and alkaline conditions,
357 with lower values for neutral conditions. For the acidic conditions, we observe that the material near
358 the wall is non-yielded, hence plug flow is seen. For the neutral condition, we observe a yielded
359 outside region, with a non-yielded central region, indicative of a Herschel-Bulkley profile.
360 At the alkaline condition, a bell-shaped superimposed on plug flow is observed, indicating a yielded
361 inside, but non-yielded outside, like the acidic conditions. The yielded regions can indicate where
362 solidification first starts, namely from the wall inwards for alkaline conditions, or from the interior
363 towards the wall for neutral conditions. For acidic conditions, it is inconclusive, as the entire material
364 has fully solidified in the middle of the cooling die. Thus, it would be of interest to investigate how
365 pH-dependent yielding behaviour determines protein melt solidification.

366 **4.3 Bulk rheology**

367 The equations/variables used for the Herschel-Bulkley-Papanastasiou model are derived from Gobes
368 et al. (2026), and are based on closed cavity rheometry on equilibrated pH-shifted SPC doughs. The
369 method of measuring hysteresis in Gobes et al. (2026) is based on a standard rheological protocol,
370 which might not accurately mimic the thermal and shear history experienced by the protein within
371 an extruder. While the current dynamic yield stress variation suffices to model flow, a specialised
372 rheometer protocol could be utilised to apply more accurate shear and thermal temporal profiles,
373 and thus to obtain a more accurate yield stress equation.

374 When the dynamic yield stress equation is used without wall slip (Eq. SI.2), a pressure drop of around
375 350 bar is required to achieve the velocities shown in Fig. 5, far higher than the 5-10 bar measured.
376 In this work, the dynamic yield stress variation was used, via which we obtained pressure drops
377 within the measured range, which indicates that we are much closer to the dynamic behaviour
378 measured in Gobes et al. (2026) as opposed to the static behaviour. Thus, using rheological
379 measurements performed outside the HME, we can adequately simulate the bulk rheology required
380 by CFD. The yield stress equation (Eq. 19) is most significantly impacted by changes in temperature
381 (Gobes et al., 2026), and thus the inclusion of heat transfer in the melt was crucial to obtaining
382 accurate pressure predictions, and thus the velocity and temperature profiles of HME.

383 A possible extension to modelling the flow is to include elastic effects via (Thixotropic)-Elasto-Visco
384 Plastic (TEVP) models instead of Herschel-Bulkley, thereby enabling simulation of more complex
385 behaviour, such as local protein-fibril alignment via a configuration tensor or moisture migration (van
386 der Sman, 2024; Fraggedakis, 2016; Souza-Mendes, 2011). Especially, the anisotropic nature of the
387 material is left to be implemented. Kaunisto et al. (2026) have proposed a local alignment parameter.
388 This parameter has no direction, and therefore could be expanded to a configuration tensor, akin to
389 work done by van der Sman et al. (2024).

390 **4.4 Multiscale alignment during flow**

391 By combining the recent finding on *in situ* protein fibril alignment at the nm-scale (Garina et al.,
392 n.d.), *ex situ* structural analysis of extruder deadstop samples (Garina et al., 2026; Kuijpers et al.,
393 2024) and the flow predictions in this work, we constructed a schematic overview of multiscale
394 structure formation in the cooling die during extrusion (Figure 5). The scheme represents the
395 situation for a low-yield dynamic stress, as observed in this work for an alkaline condition. The top
396 panel of Fig. 5 shows an initial Herschel-Bulkley velocity profile turning first into a superposition of a
397 bell-shape and plug flow, and then plug flow as the melt flows through the cooling die. In line with
398 *in situ* Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) observations (Garina et al., n.d.), the middle panel
399 shows how the initial velocity profile directs nm-scale alignment of protein fibrils. This nm-scale
400 alignment occurs due to extensional flows in the transition zone (Cornet et al., 2022), at the entrance
401 of the cooling die. The lower panel shows that upon cooling, protein fibril alignment is fixated and
402 directs phase-separation into water- and protein-rich lamellae at μm -mm length scale. The ingress
403 of the phase-separated lamellar zone towards the centre of the cooling die is in line with *ex situ*
404 measurements, by Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) (Gobes et al., 2025) and MRI (Garina
405 et al., 2026), made on samples collected upon deadstop extruder operation. The scheme depicted in
406 Fig. 5 is concurred by works investigating the effects of a breaker plate, which influences flow at the

407 entrance of the cooling die, thus impacting mm-scale phase-separated structure (Pernice et al.,
408 2025).

Figure 5: A schematic overview of structure formation at the nm- to mm-scale during flow of the protein melt through the transition zone and cooling die (CD). The transition zone is shown as the trapezoidal segment placed before the CD. The scheme represents the situation where the protein melt has a relatively low dynamic yield stress, as observed for the alkaline condition in this work. Top panel: velocity profiles for a protein melt with a low dynamic yield stress; middle panel: nm-scale protein fibril alignment; bottom panel: transition of hot protein melt to water- and protein-rich phase-separated lamellae at μm -mm scale.

409 5. Conclusions

410 This work presents a validated, scalable model that can predict the flow of a high-moisture protein
411 melt through the cooling die of an extruder. This model was created by combining a dynamic yield
412 stress τ_y , with an experimentally parametrised wall slip equation. The wall slip equation was
413 parametrised via ^1H MRI velocity measurements at different pHs and temperatures in a circular die.
414 The scalability of the model was validated by comparing the predicted and experimental temperature
415 and pressure profiles for a rectangular cooling die.

416 For further research, we recommend predicting the velocity profile in the transition zone and at the
417 start of the cooling die, as nm-scale alignment of protein fibrils is set at these locations. Upon cooling
418 and transitioning to plug flow, this nm-scale alignment directs lamellar phase-separation in protein-
419 and water-rich regions at μm -mm scale. By implementing a dynamic yield stress, together with a
420 wall slip equation, the way is paved to extend the model with the transition zone to more accurately
421 model the extensional flow as the melt enters the cooling die.

422 Data Availability

423 The COMSOL models used in this work can be found as Java files at the Zenodo data repository
424 (10.5281/zenodo.19609821), alongside experimental data for the circular and rectangular dies.

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436 **CrediT authorship contribution statement**

437 **Martijn Gobes:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualisation, Software,
438 Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualisation. **Sam**
439 **Kuijpers:** Methodology, Investigation. **Camilla Terenzi:** Writing - review & editing, Supervision,
440 Funding acquisition. **John van Duynhoven:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision,
441 Funding acquisition, Conceptualisation. **Johannes Hohlbein:** Writing – review & editing, Validation,
442 Supervision, Conceptualisation. **Ruud van der Sman:** Writing – review & editing, Validation,
443 Supervision, Conceptualization.

444

445 **Bibliography**

- 446 Akdogan, H. (1999). High moisture food extrusion. *International Journal of Food Science &*
447 *Technology*, 34(3), 195–207. <https://doi.org/10.1046/J.1365-2621.1999.00256.X>
- 448 Anker, M., Stading, M., & Hermansson, A. M. (1999). Effects of pH and the gel state on the mechanical
449 properties, moisture contents, and glass transition temperatures of whey protein films. *Journal*
450 *of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 47(5), 1878–1886.
451 <https://doi.org/10.1021/JF981115D/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/JF981115DF00010.JPEG>
- 452 Baik, O. D., & Mittal, G. S. (2003). Determination and Modeling of Thermal Properties of Tofu.
453 *International Journal of Food Properties*, 6(1), 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1081/JFP-120016621>
- 454 Barnes, E. C., Wilson, D. I., & Johns, M. L. (2006). Velocity profiling inside a ram extruder using
455 magnetic resonance (MR) techniques. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 61(5), 1357–1367.
456 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CES.2005.08.032>
- 457 Bogaard, R. H. (1985). Thermal Conductivity of Selected Stainless Steels. *Thermal Conductivity* 18,
458 175–185. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4684-4916-7_20
- 459 Cheng, S. Z. D., Lim, S., Judovits, L. H., & Wunderlich, B. (1987). Heat capacities of high melting
460 polymers containing phenylene groups. *Polymer*, 28(1), 10–22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861(87)90313-2)
461 [3861\(87\)90313-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861(87)90313-2)
- 462 Chew, D. X., Theng, A. H. P., Osen, R., & Chiang, J. H. (2025). Effects of different soy protein
463 concentrates on the structuring potential and extrudate quality of meat analogues via high
464 moisture extrusion. *Food Structure*, 45, 100448.
465 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOOSTR.2025.100448>
- 466 Chien, R. Der, Jong, W. R., & Chen, S. C. (2005). Study on rheological behavior of polymer melt
467 flowing through micro-channels considering the wall-slip effect. *Journal of Micromechanics and*
468 *Microengineering*, 15(8), 1389. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0960-1317/15/8/003>
- 469 Coelho, P. M., & Pinho, F. T. (2009). A generalized Brinkman number for non-Newtonian duct flows.
470 *J. Non-Newtonian Fluid Mech*, 156, 202–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnnfm.2008.07.001>
- 471 Corfield, G. M., Adams, M. J., Briscoe, B. J., Fryer, P. J., & Lawrence, C. J. (1999). A Critical
472 Examination of Capillary Rheometry for Foods (Exhibiting Wall Slip). *Food and Bioproducts*
473 *Processing*, 77(1), 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1205/096030899532196>
- 474 Cornet, S. H. V., Edwards, D., van der Goot, A. J., & van der Sman, R. G. M. (2020). Water release
475 kinetics from soy protein gels and meat analogues as studied with confined compression.
476 *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 66, 102528.
477 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IFSET.2020.102528>
- 478 Cornet, S. H. V., Snel, S. J. E., Lesschen, J., van der Goot, A. J., & van der Sman, R. G. M. (2021).
479 Enhancing the water holding capacity of model meat analogues through marinade composition.
480 *Journal of Food Engineering*, 290, 110283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2020.110283>
- 481 Cornet, S. H. V., Snel, S. J. E., Schreuders, F. K. G., van der Sman, R. G. M., Beyrer, M., & van der
482 Goot, A. J. (2022). Thermo-mechanical processing of plant proteins using shear cell and high-
483 moisture extrusion cooking. In *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* (Vol. 62, Number
484 12, pp. 3264–3280). Taylor and Francis Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1864618>
- 485 de Souza Mendes, P. R. (2011). Thixotropic elasto-viscoplastic model for structured fluids. *Soft*
486 *Matter*, 7(6), 2471–2483. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C0SM01021>

- 487 Ellwanger, F., Fuhrmann, M., Karbstein, H. P., & Saavedra Isusi, G. I. (2024). Influence of Lowering
488 the pH Value on the Generation of Fibrous Structures of Protein Gels with Different Network
489 Types. *Gels* 2024, Vol. 10, Page 173, 10(3), 173. <https://doi.org/10.3390/GELS10030173>
- 490 Fragedakis, D., Dimakopoulos, Y., & Tsamopoulos, J. (2016). Yielding the yield stress analysis: A
491 thorough comparison of recently proposed elasto-visco-plastic (EVP) fluid models. *Journal of*
492 *Non-Newtonian Fluid Mechanics*, 236, 104-122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnnfm.2016.09.001>
- 493 Garina, E. D., den Adel, R., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., Smith, G. N., Dalgliesh, R. M., Sztucki, M., &
494 Bouwman, W. G. (2024). SANS and SAXS: A Love Story to unravel structural evolution of soy
495 proteins and polysaccharide fibres during high moisture extrusion for meat alternatives. *Food*
496 *Hydrocolloids*, 155, 110121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2024.110121>
- 497 Garina, E. D., Gobes, M. I., Kuijpers, S. A., Saavedra Isusi, G. I., Kamman, K., Dalgliesh, R. M.,
498 Parnell, S. R., Smith, G. N., Van Duynhoven, J. P. M., & Bouwman, W. G. (n.d.). *Inside the*
499 *cooling die: in situ SANS to probe structure formation during high-moisture extrusion of soy*
500 *protein concentrate*.
- 501 Gobes, M. I., Buğday, Y., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., Hohlbein, J., & van der Sman, R. G. M. (2026).
502 Impact of pH, temperature, and moisture on the rheological behaviour of soy protein
503 concentrate doughs. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 174, 112316.
504 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2025.112316>
- 505 Garina, E. D., Kuijpers, S. A., Gobes, M. I., Sein, A., den Adel, R., Smith, G. N., Sztucki, M., Hohlbein,
506 J., Terenzi, C., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., & Bouwman, W. G. (2026). Mapping anisotropic
507 structure formation of soy protein during high-moisture extrusion. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 172,
508 112037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2025.112037>
- 509 Gobes, M. I., Kuijpers, S. A., Terenzi, C., van der Sman, R. G. M., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., & Hohlbein,
510 J. (2025). Rotated Fourier transform (RFT) enables the quantification of anisotropic structure in
511 high-moisture plant-protein extrudates. *Food Structure*, 100437.
512 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOOSTR.2025.100437>
- 513 Goyon, J., Colin, A., & Bocquet, L. (2010). How does a soft glassy material flow: finite size effects,
514 non local rheology, and flow cooperativity. *Soft Matter*, 6(12), 2668.
515 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c001930e>
- 516 Guyony, V., Fayolle, F., & Jury, V. (2023). High moisture extrusion of vegetable proteins for making
517 fibrous meat analogs: A review. *Food Reviews International*, 39(7), 4262–4287.
518 <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2021.2023816>
- 519 Högg, E., Horneber, T., & Rauh, C. (2025). Modeling and experimental analysis of protein matrix
520 solidification in cooling dies during high-moisture extrusion. *Frontiers in Food Science and*
521 *Technology*, 5, 1443376. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FRFST.2025.1443376/BIBTEX>
- 522 Högg, E., & Rauh, C. (2023). Towards a Better Understanding of Texturization during High-Moisture
523 Extrusion (HME)—Part II: Characterization of Thermophysical Properties of High-Moisture Meat
524 Analogues. *Foods*, 12(12), 2283. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS12122283>
- 525 Kaunisto, E., Öhgren, C., Lorén, N., & Stading, M. (2026). A mean-field phase separation model
526 enabling the coupling of non-isothermal flow phenomena with fibre formation in high-moisture
527 extrusion of meat analogues. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 412, 112972.
528 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2026.112972>
- 529 Kaunisto, E., Tsegaye, B., Kotzé, R., Wiklund, J., Kádár, R., & Stading, M. (2025). Towards in-line
530 rheology measurement of protein melts during high moisture extrusion by pulsed ultrasound
531 velocimetry. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 391, 112461.
532 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2024.112461>

- 533 Kaunisto, E., Wassén, S., & Stading, M. (2024). A thermodynamical finite element model of the fibre
534 formation process during extrusion of high-moisture meat analogues. *Journal of Food*
535 *Engineering*, 362, 111760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2023.111760>
- 536 Kuijpers, S. A., Garina, E. D., Gobes, M. I., Adel, R. den, Smith, G. N., Sztucki, M., Hohlbein, J.,
537 Bouwman, W. G., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., & Terenzi, C. (2025). Impact of pH-shifting on
538 multiscale structural anisotropy of high-moisture extrudates of soy proteins. *Food*
539 *Hydrocolloids*, 168, 111456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2025.111456>
- 540 Kuijpers, S. A., Goudappel, G.-J., Huppertz, T., Van Duynhoven, J., & Terenzi, C. (2024).
541 Quantification of phase separation in high moisture soy protein extrudates by NMR and MRI.
542 *Food Research International*, 197.
543 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2024.115225>
- 544 Kuijpers, S. A., Vergeldt, F., Gobes, M. I., Hohlbein, J., van Duynhoven, J. P. M., & Terenzi, C. (n.d.).
545 *Inside the cooling die: in situ MRI velocimetry to probe wall slip and yield stress during high-*
546 *moisture extrusion of soy protein concentrate.*
- 547 Kyriakopoulou, K., Dekkers, B., & van der Goot, A. J. (2018). Plant-Based Meat Analogues. In
548 *Sustainable Meat Production and Processing* (pp. 103–126). Academic Press.
549 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814874-7.00006-7>
- 550 Lawal, A., Kalyon, D. M., & Yilmazer, U. (1993). EXTRUSION AND LUBRICATION FLOWS OF
551 VISCOPLASTIC FLUIDS WITH WALL SLIP. *Chemical Engineering Communications*, 122(1), 127–
552 150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986449308936153>
- 553 Liu, H. H., & Chin, W. K. (2023). Surface Morphologies and Wettability Studies of pH-Sensitive
554 Nanofibrillated Membranes. *ChemistrySelect*, 8(35), e202301391.
555 <https://doi.org/10.1002/SLCT.202301391>
- 556 MacFarlane, D. R., & Angell, C. A. (1984). Nonexistent glass transition for amorphous solid water.
557 *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 88(4), 759–762.
558 https://doi.org/10.1021/J150648A029/ASSET/J150648A029.FP.PNG_V03
- 559 Mascia, S., Patel, M. J., Rough, S. L., Martin, P. J., & Wilson, D. I. (2006). Liquid phase migration in
560 the extrusion and squeezing of microcrystalline cellulose pastes. *European Journal of*
561 *Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 29(1), 22–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EJPS.2006.04.011>
- 562 Nieuwland, M., Heijnis, W., van der Goot, A. J., & Hamoen, R. (2023). XRT for visualizing
563 microstructure of extruded meat replacers. *Current Research in Food Science*, 6, 100457.
564 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRFS.2023.100457>
- 565 Papanastasiou, T. C. (1987). Flows of Materials with Yield. *Journal of Rheology*, 31(5), 385–404.
566 <https://doi.org/10.1122/1.549926>
- 567 Patel, M. J., Blackburn, S., & Wilson, D. I. (2017a). Modelling of paste ram extrusion subject to liquid
568 phase migration and wall friction. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 172, 487–502.
569 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CES.2017.07.001>
- 570 Patel, M. J., Blackburn, S., & Wilson, D. I. (2017b). Modelling of paste ram extrusion subject to liquid
571 phase migration and wall friction. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 172, 487–502.
572 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2017.07.001>
- 573 Pernice, L., Röhrich, D., Gaukel, V., & Leister, N. (2025). Enhancing variability in fibrous structures
574 via geometric modifications of breaker plates in high-moisture extrusion of meat analogues.
575 *Journal of Food Engineering*, 399, 112602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2025.112602>

576 Rivière, L., Caussé, N., Lonjon, A., Dantras, É., & Lacabanne, C. (2016). Specific heat capacity and
577 thermal conductivity of PEEK/Ag nanoparticles composites determined by Modulated-
578 Temperature Differential Scanning Calorimetry. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, *127*, 98–
579 104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POLYMDEGRADSTAB.2015.11.015>

580 Smetana, S., Ashtari Larki, N., Pernutz, C., Franke, K., Bindrich, U., Toepfl, S., & Heinz, V. (2018).
581 Structure design of insect-based meat analogs with high-moisture extrusion. *Journal of Food*
582 *Engineering*, *229*, 83–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2017.06.035>

583 Sui, X., Zhang, T., Zhang, X., & Jiang, L. (2025). *High-Moisture Extrusion of Plant Proteins:*
584 *Fundamentals of Texturization and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-food-072023>

585 van der Sman, R. G. M. (2012). Thermodynamics of meat proteins. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *27*(2), 529–
586 535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2011.08.016>

587 van der Sman, R. G. M., Chakraborty, P., Hua, N. P., & Kollmann, N. (2023). Scaling relations in
588 rheology of proteins present in meat analogs. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *135*, 108195.
589 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2022.108195>

590 van der Sman, R. G. M., & Meinders, M. B. J. (2011). Prediction of the state diagram of starch water
591 mixtures using the Flory–Huggins free volume theory. *Soft Matter*, *7*(2), 429–442.
592 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C0SM00280A>

593 van der Sman, R. G. M., Renzetti, S., Voudouris, P., Asghari, A., & Khalloufi, S. (2026). Correlation
594 of T2 NMR with Tg/T and viscosity. *Current Research in Food Science*, *12*, 101309.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crfs.2026.101309>

596 van der Sman, R. G. M., & van der Goot, A. J. (2009). The science of food structuring. *Soft Matter*,
597 *5*(3), 501–510. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B718952B>

598 van der Sman, R. G. M., & van der Goot, A. J. (2023). Hypotheses concerning structuring of extruded
599 meat analogs. *Current Research in Food Science*, *6*, 100510.
600 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRFS.2023.100510>

601 van der Sman, R. G. M., & Voudouris, P. (2022). *Universality in rheology of plant proteins present in*
602 *meat analogs*.

603 van der Sman, R. G. M., Voudouris, P., & Hamoen, J. R. (2024). Extrapolation of classical rheometry
604 of plant protein pastes to extrusion conditions. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *150*, 109663.
605 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2023.109663>

606 Wang, Z., Guo, W., Ding, W., Liu, K., Qin, W., Wang, C., & Wang, Z. (2023). Numerical study on the
607 hydrodynamic properties of bentonite slurries with Herschel-Bulkley-Papanastasiou rheology
608 model. *Powder Technology*, *419*, 118375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POWTEC.2023.118375>

609 Wittek, P., Ellwanger, F., Karbstein, H. P., & Emin, M. A. (2021). Morphology development and flow
610 characteristics during high moisture extrusion of a plant-based meat analogue. *Foods*, *10*(8).
611 <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10081753>

612 Wittek, P., Karbstein, H. P., & Emin, M. A. (2021). Blending Proteins in High Moisture Extrusion to
613 Design Meat Analogues: Rheological Properties, Morphology Development and Product
614 Properties. *Foods*, *10*(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS10071509>

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617 **Supplementary Information for Inside the cooling die: prediction of the flow profile of a**
618 **high-moisture soy protein melt during extrusion**

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642 **1. Brinkman number**

643 The generalised Brinkman number for laminar flow in a pipe for non-Newtonian fluids is shown in
 644 equation SI.1, as defined by Coelho & Pinho (2009). The Brinkman number is a measure of the heat
 645 transfer compared to the characteristic velocity of the system. η is the reference viscosity (2500), v
 646 the reference velocity (20 mm/s), k the thermal conductivity (0.5 W/(m·K)), and ΔT the largest
 647 thermal difference (100°C). This results in $Br \approx 0.02$, which is $\ll 1$, and thus viscous dissipation can
 648 be neglected.

$$Br \equiv \frac{\eta v^2}{k \Delta T} \quad \text{SI.1}$$

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650 **2. Pressure drop in a pipe**

651 The values used are based on typical extrusion conditions, with a temperature of 115°C, an MC of
 652 55%, and a pH of 7.1 (Gobes et al., 2026). The yield stress τ_y is taken to be constant at 10^6 Pa for
 653 the static yield stress or 10^4 Pa for the dynamic yield stress. The diameter of the pipe is defined as
 654 w [m], with z the coordinate inside the pipe [m], L the pipe length [m], k the fluid consistency index
 655 [Pa·s ^{n}], n the flow index [-], and ΔP the pressure drop over the pipe [Pa]. Other parameters are equal
 656 to those found in Table 1. The equation is adapted from Goyon et al. (2010).

$$V(z) = \frac{\Delta P}{L} \frac{1}{n} \frac{n}{\sqrt[n]{k} n + 1} \left[\left(\frac{\Delta P w}{2L} - \tau_y \right)^{\frac{n+1}{n}} - \left(\frac{\Delta P z}{2L} - \tau_y \right)^{\frac{n+1}{n}} \right] \quad \text{SI.2}$$

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658 **3. Glass transition temperature**

659 The glass transition temperature is based on work done by Gobes et al. (2026) and is derived from
 660 a weighted average of the glass transition temperature of soy protein concentrate and water. In Table
 661 SI.1, we show the constants and their values as used in the glass transition (Eq. 28).

Table SI.1: The constants and their values as used for the glass transition temperature of soy protein doughs.

Constant	Value	Source
Mass fraction of water y_w	0.65	This work
Mass fraction of soy y_s	$1 - y_w$	This work
Glass transition of water $T_{g,w}$	384 K	(van der Sman et al., 2023)
Glass transition of soy $T_{g,s}$	139 K	(MacFarlane & Angell, 1984)
Change of specific heat of water $\Delta C_{p,w}$	1.92 [kJ/(kg·K)]	(van der Sman et al., 2024)
Change of specific heat of soy $\Delta C_{p,s}$	0.425 [kJ/(kg·K)]	(van der Sman & Meinders, 2011)

662 **4. Experimental details for the circular die experiments**

Table SI.2: Experimental details for the circular die measurements. The column headers indicate the pH and T_{inlet} conditions used for the predictions.

Parameter	8.6/110	8.6/115	8.6/125	7.1/110	7.1/115	7.1/125	5.9/125
Pressure at transition Die [bar]	6	5.5	4	7.5	7.5	6	7.5
Temperature measured at transition Die [°C]	133	139	145	132.5	138	145	145

Temperature set at transition die [°C]	130	140	150	130	140	150	150
Temperature at adaptor die [°C]	111.5	116.5	124.5	110	116.5	124.5	125.5
Added acid/base [M]	0.1M NaOH	0.1M NaOH	0.1M NaOH	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.1M HCl
pH	8.6	8.4	8.7	7.1	6.9	7.3	5.9

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5. Experimental details for the rectangular die experiments

Table SI.3: Experimental details for the rectangular die experiments. In the added acid/base column, N marks Neutral conditions.

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Pressure at transition Die [bar]	9	5	10	11	6	10	8	8	8	8	10
Temperature at transition Die [°C] (T_{inlet})	127	127	127	134	134	134	141	141	141	140	140
Temperature set at transition die [°C]	130	130	130	140	140	140	150	150	150	150	150
Added acid/base [M]	N	0.1M HCl	0.1M NaOH	N	0.1M HCl	0.1M NaOH	N	0.1M HCl	0.1M NaOH	N	N
pH				7.4	4.8	8.9					
Cooling temperature [°C] (T_{cool})	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	50	35

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6. MRI images taken from the rectangular die at varying pH.

Figure SI.1: MRI images of extrudates from the rectangular cooling die. After extrusion, the samples were frozen, thawed, and swollen in water before imaging. Note that each sample had the same extruded size, but, due to swelling, the alkaline sample is larger than the acidic and neutral samples. The flow direction is along the vertical direction within the images.

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7. Numerical simulation of velocity, temperature, and pressure profiles in the circular die

670 For the circular die, three different pH values and three different T_{inlet} are simulated, resulting in nine
671 total predictions. The exact experimental values used for the pH and T_{inlet} are shown in Table SI.1.
672 For a single solution with pH = 8.4 and $T_{inlet} = 125\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the resulting temperature and velocity profiles
673 can be seen in Figure SI.2. For the temperature profiles, the cooling die wall is also included,
674 separated by the dashed line. In the velocity profile shown, we can see that the velocity profile starts
675 as a Herschel-Bulkley profile, showing a no-slip condition at the entrance of the cooling die, before
676 rapidly flattening to plug flow. This no-slip region aligns with the area where the sigmoidal
677 normalisation factor $r(x)$ is closer to 0. Detailed pressure and temperature profiles from the start to
678 the end of the die are shown in Figure SI.3 for each pH and T condition.

Figure SI.2: A) An overview of the temperature, velocity and shear rate of the circular cooling die. The simulation shown had an inlet temperature of 115°C and a pH of 7.4. B) the velocity and C) temperature profiles along the length of the cooling die at 6 equidistant lines. For the temperature profile, the cooling die is also included and marked with the dashed line.

679

680 The profile along the outside edge of the cooling die (Figure SI.3B) shows first a very slow cooling
 681 rate, as the initial section is uncooled. Afterwards, the temperature drops rapidly as the temperature
 682 difference is greatest and then slows down. This trend holds for all conditions with regard to
 683 temperature and velocity profiles, where only the magnitude or offset differs. The pressure drops
 684 show a dependency on temperatures, with a drop of around 8, 6, and 4 bar for T_{inlet} temperatures
 685 of 110, 115, and 125 °C, respectively, with an outlier for the pH 8.6/ T_{inlet} 125°C measurement, which
 686 has a pressure drop of around 11.5 (Fig SI.3A). The measured drops are around 6-7.5, 5.5-7.5, and
 687 4-6 for 110, 115, and 125 °C, respectively (Table SI.1), with high pH lowering the pressures,
 688 consistent with its effect on the yield stress.

Figure SI.3: A) All pressures show a light parabolic profile, indicating non-Newtonian behaviour. The various T_{inlet} temperatures are marked in the figure, with higher temperatures leading to lower overall pressure. B) The temperature profiles are only differentiated by inlet temperature, with pH having a negligible effect. We observe a rapid onset of cooling, after which cooling is more linear. The crosses mark the experimental data measured at position 0 (Table SI.2). They are shifted for clarity.

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8. Predicted pressure and temperature profiles along the cooling die for the rectangular die.

Figure SI.4: The pressure and temperature profiles are taken along the centreline of the width of the cooling die. The velocity at the exit is along the centreline of the width. A) The pressure profiles show a light parabolic drop, with lower inlet temperatures having higher pressures. B) The temperature has a sharp drop, with a gradual reduction to $\sim 78^{\circ}\text{C}$. There are no significant differences by pH; inlet temperature is correlated with the final temperatures. C) The velocity profiles are of plug flow, with only the model with inlet T 140°C and pH 8.9 having a slightly different profile.

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9. The sigmoidal normalised ramping function r

Figure SI.5: The normalised ramp function r used to transition from no slip (0) and the slip equation (Eq. 26). The x-axis is identical to the axis along the length of the cooling die.

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10. Pulse Diagram

Figure SI.6: Pulse diagram of the in-house developed velocimetry sequence for two consecutive acquisitions. One with a positive PFG strength and one with a negative PFG strength. Together, one set of two acquisitions can be used to calculate one flow profile. All three imaging gradients are used by the sequence to acquire a 1D velocimetry measurement. The first gradient (red) is used to spatially encode the signal in the read direction (x-direction), the second gradient (green) to encode motion in the flow direction (y-direction), and the third gradient (blue) to select the imaging slice (z-direction). Slice selection is required to prevent averaging of the signal originating from the material near the cooling die wall that is out-of-plane with the signal originating from the material at the in-plane centre of the cooling die. A low-power slice-selective pulse is given for excitation, and a hard refocusing pulse is used. The sampling rate is set to 100 kHz. As shown in the diagram, the following parameters are used: TE = 17 ms, TR = 1 s, PFG strength respectively is 16 mT/m and -16 mT/m for the first and second acquisition.

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